

The Curriculum Construction Of Yunnan Minority Music In Vocal Singing Major Of Yunnan Colleges And Universities In China From The Perspective Of Applied Ethnomusicology

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Abstract

Among Chinese vocal singing majors, the vocal singing majors in Yunnan universities have their own unique characteristics. Its rich minority music resources help to give advantages in building the special courses. In order to be able to conform to the needs and development of the times and meet its own construction and status, the vocal singing majors in Yunnan universities should devote themselves to inherit and carry forward the excellent Yunnan minority music, strengthen the combination of theory and practice in the construction of the curriculum of vocal singing majors, optimize the curriculum, create exclusive characteristic teaching materials, formulate reasonable talent training programs, and cultivate excellent vocal talents with local characteristics. This paper uses the perspective of applied ethnomusicology to create a new model of Yunnan minority music education and non-heritage culture transmission. In the construction of the curriculum of vocal singing majors in local colleges and universities, the development laws of the times and policies are met, Yunnan minority music is implanted in the teaching of vocal singing majors, the advantages of local characteristics are brought into play, and application and integration are practically achieved in the interactive relationship between applied ethnomusicology and vocal singing majors' educational disciplines.

Introduction

With regard to the current research direction of the author, the curriculum construction of Yunnan minority music in vocal singing majors in Yunnan universities, the author has made a detailed summary and generalization in the existing literature reviewed and referred to. In the existing literature, the author has reviewed and referred to 49 journals, 4 master's theses, and 23 monographs, including 3 ethnomusicology monographs with theoretical applications, in order to summarize the relevant academic papers and monographs on Yunnan minority music and the curriculum construction of vocal singing majors and other majors. This chapter summarizes the literature review from Yunnan minority music, Yunnan minority music education, research related to the cultivation of minority vocal talents based on university platform, research related to the construction of professional curriculum, research on minority education philosophy, and research on applied ethnomusicology theory, as follows.

A review related to the content of the study

Through the author's preliminary compilation, the existing literature is sorted out from five specific aspects, namely, Yunnan minority music, Yunnan minority music education, minority music education transmission, minority music curriculum construction, and music education philosophy.

Research related to Yunnan minority music

In the literature reviewed by the author, there are 43 studies on Yunnan minority music, 40 studies on minority music, 9 studies on minority folk music, 9 studies on Yunnan folk music, and 9 studies on Yunnan minority music culture in the literature reviewed on the China Knowledge Network. As shown in the figure below, the literature review study in this section can help the author to clearly understand the development, use, and transmission of traditional minority music in Yunnan's rich minority music.

Huang Rui & Lu Yuan (2017) and Luo Shuxuan (2012) they introduce the artistic characteristics of Yunnan minority music in terms of its diversity, vividness, and aesthetics, and then talk about how to inherit it in the form of developing minority music resources into products and moving them to the stage. The duties of mass cultural workers are mentioned, and the need to pay close attention to the inheritance and protection of minority music culture. This can serve as a reference for the author in the study of curriculum construction of non-genetic inheritance.

The music of Yunnan's ethnic minorities is mainly transmitted orally, and the differences in singing forms and styles are due to the local human environment, living habits, language and religious beliefs. Therefore, the melodies heard by the public are very special, regional and ethnic. The folk music of Yunnan's ethnic minorities not only has high aesthetic value, but also contains a wealth of humanistic and aesthetic ideas. She not only introduces the current situation of Yunnan's minority folk music, but also offers some personal insights into the preservation and transmission of minority folk music. First, the quality of art should be improved both in terms of contemporary communication values and audience aesthetics. The development of ethnic minority folk music under the threshold of communication should be expanded through mass media, internet, television, radio, etc. Second, the dissemination of music education media in universities should be strengthened. Third, to protect minority folk music through the inheritance of organizations such as biography museums and cultural centers.

In the literature collected by the author, for the papers related to Yunnan minority music education, the way and method of applying minority music elements to the vocal singing profession, not only from the full use of singing, but also in the corresponding theoretical quality courses, can be fully used, and can play a good heritage at the same time of education. The following author summarizes and outlines a few representative relevant papers.

Xi Liu (2011) and Shengjuan Yang (2017) used the relationship between minority music and sight-reading to elaborate the significance of music education from the perspective of sight-reading and ear training. This can provide rich curriculum materials for the author in developing curriculum construction. To explore and study Chinese minority music as a way to establish a Chinese approach to teaching sight-singing and ear training based on the mother tongue. Promote our ethnic music culture and improve students' musical aesthetics. To guide students' awareness of Chinese minority music elements through the diversity of constructed music and musical styles. The addition of minority music elements to the sight-singing and ear training can improve students' musical aesthetics and musical literacy, while improving their ability to read and sing music. Secondly, by learning to sing and practice classical and outstanding ethnic music works, students can gain a deeper understanding of the value of music. This will not only lay a good foundation for students' creativity, but also broaden their horizons.

Bu Guangyi (2022) used the current situation of music and culture education in Yunnan region as a case study, Li Chenglong (2019) used minority music elements to combine with college education, and Zhang Jin (2021) mentioned how the vocal classroom in Chinese colleges and universities integrates ethnic elements. The three authors' discussion can clarify the importance of integrating ethnic minorities into school learning, ethnic vocal music Luo Hongmin (2015) and Xu Jun and Ma Ming (2020) both mention the heritage and protection of music of ethnic minorities in border areas at the same time, and the integration of ethnic music in college vocal classes can effectively enrich the music classroom; strengthen the practice of ethnic music, improve the teaching level, and teachers lead students to study the spirit of ethnic culture in depth connotation while also achieving how to inherit and protect minority music.

Firstly, we start from three aspects: school, family and society, and work together to convey the correct concept of music education. Secondly, we give full play to the advantages of multi-ethnic education, tap the local minority music education materials, and fully guarantee the inheritance and development of minority music. By analyzing the current situation of minority music in the border areas of Yunnan, it is very necessary to protect and inherit the music culture of the border minority areas. How to guide how to improve the artistic cultivation of the minority groups in the border area and carry forward the minority music culture can only achieve the stability and prosperity that is beneficial to the minority areas in the border area.

Ethnic music elements should be combined with the teaching of vocal music in colleges and universities. Ethnic music which contains a very rich connotation, from the single situation of China's current college vocal music teaching, the integration of combining ethnic music elements can promote the further development of China's college vocal music teaching. The application of the art of minority music elements in college vocal teaching is not only to add ethnic music elements in vocal performance to improve students' music literacy, but also to increase the application of minority musical instruments to enrich college music education and improve students' interest in learning, and to improve the traditional teaching method of using multimedia to show minority music to increase students' understanding of minority music and improve teaching, and to integrate minority music into teaching materials. The teachers should encourage students to read more books related to ethnic music elements to improve students' ethnic self-confidence.

Conclusion

In her study, Jane Zhang (2021) mainly proposed that in folk music has a unique style charm and it is necessary to combine East and West in college vocal music teaching. The integration of Chinese folk culture in the college vocal classroom is more effective in improving students' singing ability and expression as well as making them more aware of Chinese folk music and improving their national self-confidence. In this paper, we will study how to carry out the integration of Chinese folk culture in college vocal classroom: by carrying out folk music theory courses to introduce the integration of folk music in college vocal classroom, effectively

enriching the music classroom; strengthening the practice of folk music, improving the teaching level, and teachers leading students to study the spiritual connotation of folk culture in depth.

According to Jun Xu and Ming Ma (2020), Yunnan minority music is shaped by geography, social development patterns and historical evolution. The inheritance of minority music needs to be realized through education, but the influence of Western music theory system is very unfavorable to the inheritance and development of minority music, and only through paying attention and importance to the inheritance and protection of minority music can minority music be carried forward. This requires us to develop a strategy for the preservation and protection of minority music in Yunnan in a systematic manner. First, to improve the ethnicity of music education in Yunnan universities, and to discover and value minority Yunnan music resources. Second, encourage students to go deeper into the fields and states to collect music and experience the charm of minority music. Third, ensure the continuation of education for minority talents, and cultivate and select outstanding minority talents. Fourth, develop diversified means of promoting minority music in conjunction with tourism development. Only through the implementation of an orderly, well-planned strategy can Yunnan's minority music culture be better passed on and carried forward.

Through the studies of several authors above, it is possible to learn insights into the integration of Yunnan folk music into vocal singing as well as the transmission of traditional minority music. The author develops his research through his own topics, not only to integrate Yunnan folk music into his own teaching system, as well as non-genetic inheritance, but more importantly, to establish an independent curriculum system and build a teaching model with local characteristics.

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